

“TECH-ENHANCED LEARNING: INNOVATIONS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES”

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Abstract: The attention paid in our country to foreign language teaching in this country, as well as English language. There is information on how to use new advanced technologies in English. Teaching English should start with preschool education, so that the child thinks earlier, acquires more knowledge earlier. The use of innovative technologies is a modern requirement, so it would be appropriate to teach in English using innovative technologies.

Key words: foreign language, teaching, technologies, preschool, education, child, knowledge, modern requirement.

INTRODUCTION: Language teacher development is essential for the effective use of technology for language teaching. This chapter explores digital language teaching and presents a digital language teacher development framework, which can be considered as a resource for language teachers’ professional development in technology-enhanced language teaching (TELT). The chapter also discusses teacher engagement with professional development in terms of exploration, communication, collaboration and reflection (ECCR) and offers discussion questions for those who want to reflect further on the topics addressed in the chapter.

METHODOLOGY

With the rapid development of computer technology and the improvement of the value of the information society, it is undergoing dramatic changes in relation to the acquisition of knowledge. These dramatic changes brought about by ICT have brought a new paradigm to education. Currently, multimedia technology, network technology and satellite technology transfer, as a representative of information technology, is developing very rapidly.

Modern educational technologies based on information technologies play an important role in promoting the modernization of education. Modern educational technologies will have a significant impact on ideas, forms, process, teaching methods and education management. Applying modern education technologies to teach English will be the driving force behind continuing education innovations. Using the modern theory of education and modern information technologies will allow achieving the effective development of teaching a foreign language.

New educational innovations have already arrived in Uzbekistan. For example, computer technology has allowed teachers to make their lessons more interactive and therefore more interesting and useful; this method has also been shown to improve student performance, as lessons are more memorable, and therefore students are able to more effectively store information. Teachers, like students, can also find a range of resources on the Internet that can provide inspiration and advice for classes; teachers can also recommend good resources for students to further encourage and stimulate their learning.

In addition to computers, many schools and colleges use new technology methods to enhance learning experiences; they include digital television channels, DVDs, digital radio, and sophisticated forms of communication technology. Digital radio and television allow students to access a huge variety of channels that span the time range of various subjects, including languages, science, history and geography, to name just a few. Students got used to the new technology as they grew up with it; therefore, it is undoubtedly beneficial that they have the opportunity to use it to increase their ability to learn and to defend their interests. Programmers and educational tackles are now widely available for download to your computer or

MP3player; This makes education more modern and multifaceted. With the invention of new technologies, students can be exposed to more English text in a multimedia language environment. In the fast-paced 21st century, various innovative technologies are being introduced to teach English in classrooms.

The knowledge base is quickly double and triple in such a short time. In order to cope with this trend, we must use modern technology to teach students English in Uzbekistan. Students should update their knowledge using modern technology. Otherwise, they will be lowered in the labor market. The number of reading on any topic and in many languages is now available on the Internet, and the opportunity to participate in discussions with people from all walks of life is a motivation for many students.

More than a process of communication, trade and transactions, today the technology is widely used in the educational sectors. Despite the fact that technology cannot play the teacher’s vital words, it can be used as an additional tool to enhance classroom teaching methods. Like an ordinary chalk and the way of speaking, it seems monotonous and boring for students, teachers, and emphasis on the latest technology for teaching subjects. Various types of software and modern technology are being introduced to enable students to access using their subjects easily. Every day, people get access to some new technologies that connect their hand with teaching English.

CONCLUSION

This chapter has presented the ECCR-based DLTDF as a working guide to language teachers in digital environments. It has looked at the suggested levels of teacher engagement with each component of the framework and pointed out the importance of finding out what professional development activities are employed by digital language teachers and how much the teachers use the 11 activities to improve their competence in digital language teaching.

Teachers are encouraged to move to a higher level of the framework while developing knowledge and skills for effective language teaching. There is a need for empirical studies of the effectiveness of language teacher development using the

frame work and the use of digital language teaching strategies in various contexts. Findings of those studies will deepen our understanding of language teacher development in the digital age.

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